

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Creating 2D Reference Illustrations for Functional Tissue Units

Planning and creating 2D illustrations of functional tissue units (FTUs)

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Introduction

This SOP describes the procedures for designing and creating 2D illustrations of functional tissue units (FTUs). FTUs are defined as the smallest tissue organization that performs a unique physiologic function and is replicated multiple times in a whole organ. Due to the open source nature of the Human Reference Atlas (HRA), we hope these principles can be applied to continued work for the HRA, and as a starting point for anyone looking to develop 2D illustrations for related projects. The primary audience for this SOP is illustrators.

Roles and Responsibilities

The **Medical Illustrator** draws functional tissue units (FTUs), which include anatomical structures (AS) and cell types (CT).

The **Subject Matter Expert (SME)** is an organ subject matter expert with deep domain knowledge of the FTU who has agreed to serve as the technical advisor and reviewer. The SME is responsible for ensuring the anatomical and biological accuracy of the FTU.

The **Principal Investigator (PI)** approves budgets associated with FTU illustration construction, sets high-level goals and associated deadlines, attends meetings, and reviews and comments on notes and recordings from relevant meetings between the Medical Illustrator, Subject Matter Experts, and other key personnel as needed.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
Medical Illustrator	Rachel Bajema	rbajema@iu.edu
Subject Matter Expert (SME)	Depends on the FTU	
Principal Investigator (PI)	Katy Börner	katy@indiana.edu

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Procedures

Preparing to illustrate a functional tissue unit (FTU)

These procedures outline the process of planning a 2D illustration and some considerations that may occur at this stage.

- Consult the ASCT+B (Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers) table for a given organ to get a list of anatomical structures and cell types that are known to exist in the FTU. The ASCT+B table should be approved by an appropriate SME and the PI before beginning the illustration process. This ensures that all important anatomical structures and cell types are captured.
- Research at this stage should include an understanding of the size and scale of the FTU in relation to its organ system, as well as an understanding of the shape and size of the anatomical structures and cell types to be illustrated. Also of interest is any known data on the total number of cells present in the FTU, or number and distribution of cells by type, plus supported data or scholarly publications. All sources used (e.g., publications, experimental data) need to be documented and will be published as part of the DOI'd metadata for the FTU.
- Identify key histological visualizations to anchor your illustration within a data-based context. Keep track of and cite relevant scholarly papers, books and other references and publish those as part of the DOI'd metadata for the FTU.
- An understanding of basic illustration standards within the medical illustration field for a given FTU will be helpful. For example, how are illustrators representing villi, generalized cell shape(s), or any specialized structures within a given FTU?
- Consult the [HuBMAP illustration template and HRA style guide](#) for an understanding of how to construct and color the illustration. Note that there are a range of colors available.
- Understand the relevant surrounding anatomy. It may be helpful to illustrate ~10-20% of the surrounding anatomy in order to give the FTU illustration context within the larger organ system.

Technical illustration process

- Create a pencil sketch of the FTU in detail to the cellular level. The goal is to represent every individual cell in the FTU that would be visible in a 2D cutting plane.
- Scan your sketch at 300 dpi and place it on the "Art" layer in Adobe Illustrator. Run "Image Trace" on the "Shades of Gray" setting, and expand the result. This creates a vectorized version of your sketch, which can be easily resized without loss of detail. Select the sketch and set it to "Multiply" under the "Transparency" menu. Lock this layer.
- Separate cell types as you color them based on the ASCT+B table so that each anatomical structure (AS) or cell type (CT) is on its own layer. If multiple AS or CT need to be illustrated as a single object and not broken out by individual AS/cells, put this object on a new layer. This might be needed for AS-level illustrations, or for larger FTUs such as nephron of the kidney.

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

- Name layers based on the AS/CT “Label” terms found in the ASCT+B table.
- Colorize your illustration based on the colors found in the color palette and using the conventions of nucleus colors appearing darker than the cell fills. Cells should be filled with solid colors and not use gradients for shading. Solid brushwork should be used for cell outlines.
- The final outline should surround the entire FTU and be the thickest outline in the illustration. This should use variable lineweight to give some dimensionality to the FTU and add visual interest.
- A scale bar and the “H” blood cell icon (with H for Human) should be added in the lower right-hand corner.
- Illustrations should be saved in .svg format.
- The illustrator sends the illustration to the SME and PI for technical review. Comments are shared via email and sketches. A meeting might be arranged to resolve questions.
- Any changes should be resolved and edits made before publication on the HuBMAP portal.

Illustration considerations and concerns

- The current stated purpose of the illustrations is to help clarify the data available in the HuBMAP portal, and to bridge the gap between the data described in the ASCT+B tables and the histological visualizations of experimental data. As far as possible, all AS/CT “Label” terms in the ASCT+B table that are marked as FTU should be included.
- Occasionally, spaces may be labeled and included in the drawing if necessary for visual clarification. In this case, the term will not be in the ASCT+B table but may be included with SME approval. An example is the nuclear pore of the alveolus of the lung.
- The illustrations should serve as an ideal view of the FTUs, pulling vital information on the cell types, shapes, and general appearance from the histology, but also serving to illustrate visual components that may not exist in any given data slice, or otherwise visually clarifying or enhancing functional information.
- In some cases, it may be necessary to add dimensionality to the illustration that goes beyond what may be visible in any given 2D slice. For example, the renal corpuscle may need added depth that can show the 3D nature of the capillary structure present in this FTU, whereas the Crypts of Lieberkuhn may give an accurate structural representation without showing a depth dimension to the structure.
- FTUs may be nested, or exist within larger FTU structures. An example of this is the nephron of the kidney, which is an FTU on its own, but includes many smaller FTUs within its structure (renal corpuscle, cortical collecting duct, etc.)
- The illustrations should work well when presented next to histological data, as well as the 3D models being developed in conjunction with this project.
- The illustrations should remain editable (not rasterized), and open for regular updates in order to reflect guidance from SMEs or other relevant contributors, and to include new data and cell types as they become available.

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

- The 2D illustrations may be used to help train machine learning algorithms and should depict firm cell boundaries and well-defined individual cell types when possible.

References

Bono, Bernard de, Pierre Grenon, Richard Baldock, and Peter Hunter. “Functional Tissue Units and Their Primary Tissue Motifs in Multi-Scale Physiology.” *Journal of Biomedical Semantics* 4, no. 1 (October 8, 2013): 22–22. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2041-1480-4-22>.

Börner, Katy, Sarah A. Teichmann, Ellen M. Quardokus, James C. Gee, Kristen Browne, David Osumi-Sutherland, Bruce W. Herr, et al. “Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers of the Human Reference Atlas.” *Nature Cell Biology* 23, no. 11 (November 1, 2021): 1117–28. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41556-021-00788-6>.

Glossary

ASCT+B Tables: Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers (ASCT+B) Tables are authored by multiple experts across many consortia. The tables capture the partonomy of anatomical structures, cell types and major biomarkers (e.g., gene, protein, lipid or metabolic markers).

Functional tissue unit (FTU): A functional tissue unit is the smallest tissue organization that performs a unique physiologic function and is replicated multiple times in a whole organ.